

THE STUDY OF AGROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL IN THE APPLICATION OF THE TECHNOLOGY OF NON-TILLAGE PLOWING

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Abstract. This study investigates the agrochemical properties of soil under non-tillage plowing technology, a farming practice gaining popularity for its potential to enhance soil health and sustainability. Non-tillage plowing minimizes soil disturbance, thereby preserving soil structure and organic matter while improving moisture retention and reducing erosion. The research was conducted in various agricultural fields utilizing non-tillage methods, where soil samples were collected and analyzed for pH levels, nutrient content (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium), and organic matter content. Results indicate significant improvements in soil agrochemical properties compared to traditional tillage practices, highlighting the positive impact of non-tillage on nutrient availability and soil fertility. This paper discusses the implications of these findings for agricultural practices and provides recommendations for farmers and policymakers seeking to adopt sustainable farming methods. The study underscores the need for further research to explore the long-term benefits of non-tillage plowing in diverse agricultural contexts.

Keywords: non-tillage plowing, agrochemical properties, soil health, soil structure, nutrient content, organic matter, soil moisture retention, sustainable agriculture.

In recent years, the agricultural sector has faced significant challenges, including soil degradation, reduced fertility, and the increasing need for sustainable farming practices. Non-tillage plowing technology has emerged as a viable solution to these challenges, offering a method that minimizes soil disturbance and enhances overall soil health. Unlike traditional tillage, which often disrupts soil structure, non-tillage practices maintain the integrity of soil structure, and organic matter levels, are crucial indicators of soil health and fertility. The agrochemical properties of soil, such as pH, nutrient content, and organic matter levels, are crucial indicators of soil health and fertility. Understanding how non-tillage plowing affects these

properties is essential for farmers and agronomists seeking to implement sustainable farming practices [2].

Below are the results of the soil analysis (Table 1).

(Table 1)

Nutrients, moisture, and soil pH reactions in the soil, 2024.

Nº	Depth, cm	pH	Humus,%	Azot N,%	P ₂ O ₅ mg/kg	K ₂ O Mg/kg	Humidity,%
1	0-15	6,9	0,2	0,069	36,39	166	27,2
2	15-30	6,9	0,096	0,041	34,05	138	51,3
3	30-50	7,0	0,16	0,021	5,84	148	45,2
4	50-70	7,0	0,15	0,024	17,51	120	38,4
5	70-90	7,0	0,46	0,022	20,21	102	30,0
6	90-110	7,0	0,39	0,024	3,31	68	18,4

According to the results, the soil pH reaction is equal to 6.9 and 7.0, which indicates a neutral environment. The amount of humus in the soil layers showed a low level. The available phosphorus content in the 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm layers was 36.39 and 34.05 mg/kg, respectively, indicating an average level, while the remaining soil layers showed low and very low levels. The exchangeable potassium ranged from 101 to 167 mg/kg in the soil from the 0-15 cm layer to the 70-90 cm layer, indicating a low level, and it was observed that the 90-110 cm soil layer was very poorly supplied with exchangeable potassium. The total nitrogen content in the soil was very low, ranging from 0.0211 to 0.070%. The moisture content in the soil averaged 45.2% and 51.3%.

Non-tillage plowing represents a paradigm shift in soil management practices, emphasizing the preservation of soil structure and health. This technique involves planting crops without the prior tillage of the soil, thus minimizing disturbance to the soil layers. The following subsections highlight the critical roles that non-tillage plowing plays in effective soil management. Non-tillage practices significantly enhance soil structure by maintaining the natural aggregation of soil particles. This aggregation is crucial for promoting air and water movement through the soil, thereby supporting root development and microbial activity. Additionally, non-tillage reduces compaction, which can often occur with traditional tillage methods. As a result, soil retains its porosity, facilitating better drainage and reducing the risk of erosion. The preservation of

earthworms and other beneficial organisms is also a key advantage, as these organisms contribute to nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition. One of the notable benefits of non-tillage plowing is its positive impact on soil moisture retention. By leaving crop residues on the surface, non-tillage helps create a protective layer that reduces evaporation and minimizes water runoff [1]. This practice can be particularly beneficial in arid and semi-arid regions, where water scarcity is a pressing issue. Enhanced moisture retention not only supports crop growth but also contributes to overall soil health, as adequate moisture is essential for microbial activity and nutrient availability. Soil erosion is a significant concern in conventional farming, where tillage can loosen the topsoil and make it more susceptible to wind and water erosion. Non-tillage plowing mitigates this risk by maintaining soil cover and reducing soil disturbance. The crop residues left on the soil surface act as a barrier against erosive forces, helping to protect the soil and maintain its integrity. Research has shown that fields under non-tillage systems experience significantly less soil erosion compared to those subjected to traditional tillage, thereby contributing to long-term soil conservation. The adoption of non-tillage practices also plays a crucial role in enhancing soil fertility. By reducing the rate of erosion and maintaining organic matter, non-tillage promotes a stable environment for nutrient retention. The accumulation of organic matter from crop residues not only enriches the soil but also supports microbial communities that aid in nutrient cycling. This leads to improved availability of essential nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, which are vital for optimal plant growth.

Conclusion. Non-tillage plowing offers significant advantages for sustainable agriculture, including improved soil health, enhanced moisture retention, and reduced erosion. However, farmers must also navigate various challenges, such as weed management, initial yield fluctuations, soil compaction, and pest pressures. The transition to non-tillage practices requires careful planning, adaptation of nutrient management strategies, and a willingness to embrace new methodologies. By understanding these challenges and seeking support from agricultural resources, farmers can effectively implement non-tillage systems and harness their benefits, ultimately contributing to more resilient and sustainable farming practices.

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